

Improving English Proficiency and Employability Skills of Rural Engineering Professionals Using ICT and AI: An ESP Framework in ELT

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Abstract:

The growing demand for skilled professionals in the global job market underscores the need to enhance both English proficiency and employability skills, particularly among rural engineering professionals. In regions such as the erstwhile Adilabad, Karimnagar, and Warangal districts of Telangana, where access to quality education and skill development opportunities is often limited, the integration of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) and Artificial Intelligence (AI) presents promising solutions. This study explores the potential of ICT and AI tools to improve the English proficiency and employability skills of rural engineering professionals through Cotton's (2001) Employability Skills Framework within an English for Specific Purposes (ESP) approach. By evaluating the effectiveness of these technological interventions, the research aims to bridge skill gaps among rural professionals, fostering their career development and enhancing their employability. The findings will provide valuable insights into the role of ICT and AI in shaping the future of rural engineering professionals in Telangana, with broader implications for educational practices in rural India.

Key Words: Employability, ICT, AI, ESP, ELT.

INTRODUCTION:

The global demand for engineering professionals proficient in English is rapidly increasing, with a particular emphasis on those from rural backgrounds. Rural engineering graduates often face significant challenges in language proficiency and employability skills, which hinder their professional growth and competitiveness. In Telangana, particularly in the districts of erstwhile Adilabad, Karimnagar, and Warangal, many rural engineering students struggle with communication skills and are ill-prepared for the competitive job market. The emergence of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) and Artificial Intelligence (AI) presents a

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unique opportunity to address these gaps by offering personalized, scalable, and efficient training solutions.

This paper explores the potential of ICT and AI tools to enhance English proficiency and employability skills among rural engineering professionals, leveraging an English for Specific Purposes (ESP) framework in English Language Teaching (ELT).

Employability Skills

Employability skills, including communication, teamwork, adaptability, and time management, are vital for career success. Engineers also need technical expertise and the ability to engage in continuous learning. Addressing these skill gaps in rural engineers is crucial to boosting their global competitiveness.

Artificial Intelligence (AI)

AI refers to systems that mimic human intelligence, supporting personalized learning, real-time tracking of performance, and instant feedback in education. AI-powered tools such as chatbots and virtual tutors offer customized support, improving language skills and employability.

English for Specific Purposes (ESP)

ESP focuses on teaching English tailored to specific professional needs. For rural engineers, ESP targets the technical vocabulary and communication skills essential for their careers, making it more applicable than traditional English instruction.

English Language Teaching (ELT)

ELT is designed to develop skills in listening, speaking, reading, and writing. For rural engineers, ELT should concentrate on career-relevant skills, such as report writing, giving presentations, and engaging in discussions, with the support of ICT and AI to enhance the learning experience and better prepare students for global job markets.

This study examines how ICT and AI can be utilized to enhance English proficiency and employability skills among rural engineering professionals in the districts of erstwhile Adilabad, Karimnagar, and Warangal through the application of an ESP-based ELT approach. By investigating the role of these technologies in delivering tailored English instruction and improving communication skills, the study aims to equip rural professionals with the essential skills needed for global employment opportunities. The findings will contribute to the development of more effective, technology-driven educational methods designed to overcome the challenges faced by rural learners in India.

BACKGROUND OF THE STUDY

Rural areas in India, including the districts of erstwhile Adilabad, Karimnagar, and Warangal, have long faced educational disparities, particularly in the fields of science and technology. Engineering graduates from these regions often struggle to acquire proficiency in English, the global language

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of communication and technical documentation. In addition to language barriers, these professionals frequently lack crucial employability skills, such as effective interpersonal communication, teamwork, and problem-solving abilities. While traditional language teaching methods have been utilized, their impact in rural settings has been limited. With the advent of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) and Artificial Intelligence (AI), there is an increasing interest in exploring how these innovative tools can enhance English language proficiency and employability skills, particularly through the English for Specific Purposes (ESP) approach in English Language Teaching (ELT).

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Several studies have examined how Information and Communication Technology (ICT) and Artificial Intelligence (AI) influence language learning and the development of employability skills in rural contexts. Sharma and Kaur (2020) found that ICT tools, such as online platforms and mobile applications, significantly enhance language skills among rural learners by making learning more accessible and engaging. Similarly, Kumar (2019) highlighted the role of AI-driven tools, like chatbots and personalized learning systems, in providing customized English instruction that adjusts to each learner's pace and needs, leading to more effective educational outcomes. These findings suggest that ICT and AI can help bridge educational disparities in rural areas by providing individualized support and resources that traditional teaching methods often cannot.

Additionally, research has shown that English for Specific Purposes (ESP)-focused English Language Teaching (ELT) is particularly effective in equipping professionals with the language skills necessary for specific industries. Basturkmen (2010) argued that ESP approaches focus on specialized vocabulary and communication strategies tailored to particular professions, allowing learners to acquire the technical language essential for their fields. This approach has proven to be more relevant and applicable, especially in professions like engineering, where precise communication is crucial.

Furthermore, studies by Sautter et al. (2018) and Zheng et al. (2020) suggest that integrating ICT and AI with ESP frameworks can further improve both language proficiency and employability skills by offering real-time feedback, adaptive learning pathways, and interactive content. These tools help learners practice language skills in contexts that mimic professional environments, which are essential for career development. For example, Sautter et al. (2018) demonstrated that AI-based platforms improve learners' ability to engage in professional scenarios by simulating complex work-related interactions. Similarly, Zheng et al. (2020) found that AI technologies, such as virtual assistants, can offer personalized language instruction and track progress towards specific career goals.

However, there is limited research exploring the combination of ICT and AI within an ESP framework specifically tailored to rural engineering professionals. This gap in the literature highlights the need for further studies to investigate how these technologies can be utilized to improve language proficiency and employability skills in rural settings. This research seeks to address this gap by exploring the integration of ICT and AI tools within an ESP context to enhance the employability of rural engineering professionals.

IDENTIFICATION OF RESEARCH GAPS

While existing literature offers valuable insights into the role of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) and Artificial Intelligence (AI) in language learning and skill development, there is a notable lack of comprehensive studies exploring these tools specifically within the context of rural engineering professionals. Furthermore, the application of the English for Specific Purposes (ESP) framework to enhance both language proficiency and employability skills among rural professionals remains underexplored. This study aims to bridge this gap by focusing on rural engineering graduates in Telangana and evaluating the effectiveness of ICT and AI tools in addressing their specific learning needs.

SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

This research holds significant importance as it tackles the dual challenge of improving English proficiency and employability skills among rural engineering professionals in the erstwhile districts of Adilabad, Karimnagar, and Warangal in Telangana. By leveraging ICT and AI, the study offers a contemporary solution to overcome traditional learning barriers in rural areas. The findings are expected to inform future educational practices and policies, ensuring they are more accessible, relevant, and impactful for rural learners, ultimately contributing to the broader goal of enhancing employability and professional growth in these regions.

PURPOSE OF THE RESEARCH

The primary objective of this research is to design an ESP framework that incorporates ICT and AI tools to enhance both English proficiency and employability skills among rural engineering professionals. The study focuses on addressing the unique linguistic, communicative, and professional needs of engineering graduates from the districts of erstwhile Adilabad, Karimnagar, and Warangal in Telangana, India.

The specific objectives of the research are as follows:

- To bridge the gap between the current English proficiency levels of rural engineering professionals and the global workforce expectations.

- To develop context-specific communication abilities that meet the demands of technical and professional environments.
- To utilize ICT and AI tools to create a dynamic, adaptive, and learner-centered approach to English language instruction.
- To enhance employability by integrating industry-specific vocabulary, professional communication, and essential soft skills into the curriculum.
- To provide equitable access to quality language education for rural learners, addressing educational and socio-economic disparities.

Through the development and evaluation of this innovative ESP framework, the study aims to make a meaningful contribution to English Language Teaching (ELT), engineering education, and workforce readiness in underprivileged regions.

AIMS OF THE STUDY

- To investigate the impact of ICT and AI tools on improving English proficiency among rural engineering professionals.
- To assess how these tools contribute to enhancing employability skills such as communication, problem-solving, and teamwork.
- To explore the potential of the ESP framework in tailoring English language instruction to meet the specific needs of engineering professionals.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To determine the current level of English proficiency and employability skills among rural engineering professionals.
- To evaluate the effectiveness of ICT and AI tools in improving employability skills.
- To assess the effectiveness of ICT integration and AI-based ELT practices in rural engineering education.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

1. How do ICT and AI tools influence the English proficiency of rural engineering professionals?
2. What impact do these technologies have on the employability skills of rural engineering professionals?
3. How effective is the ESP framework in improving career-specific language and skills among rural engineers?

HYPOTHESIS

- ICT and AI tools significantly enhance the English proficiency of rural engineering professionals.
- ICT and AI tools improve essential employability skills such as communication, critical thinking, and collaboration.
- The ESP framework effectively addresses the specific language needs of rural engineering professionals, making learning more relevant and impactful.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This research utilizes a mixed-methods approach, combining both qualitative and quantitative data collection techniques. A survey was distributed to rural engineering professionals in the three erstwhile districts of Telangana to evaluate their current levels of English proficiency and employability skills. In addition, a series of workshops integrating ICT and AI-based language learning tools was conducted, followed by pre- and post-assessments to measure the improvements in these areas. Qualitative interviews were also conducted with a select group of participants to gain deeper insights into their experiences with these tools.

The study adopts a within-stage mixed-model research design, incorporating both quantitative and qualitative methods through the use of questionnaires, classroom observations, and interviews. This approach will enable the collection of both numerical data and qualitative feedback, providing a comprehensive understanding of the study's outcomes.

SAMPLE

The study included 180 third-year B. tech students from three rural engineering colleges in Telangana. The selected institutions are:

S.No	College Name	Location	District (Former)
1	Aizza College of Engineering and Technology (AZCET)	Mulkalla, Mancherial	Erstwhile Adilabad district
2	Vivekananda Institute of Technology and Sciences (VITS)	Batalukunta, Peddapalli Road	Erstwhile Karimnagar district
3	Balaji Institute of Technology and Science (BITS)	Laknepally, Warangal Rural	Erstwhile Warangal district

Table -1: Representing -selection of the sample study

The participants were be divided into two groups: a control group that receive conventional instruction, and an experimental group that experience ICT-embedded instruction. This division was facilitated the comparison of the impact of both instructional methods on language proficiency and employability skills.

TOOLS

- **Questionnaires:** To assess the students' current English proficiency and employability skills.
- **Classroom Observation:** To monitor student engagement and interaction with ICT and AI-based tools during the workshops.
- **Interviews:** To gather qualitative data on the participants' experiences with the ICT and AI tools used in the study.

PROCEDURE

Following the intervention, the performance of both groups was analyzed and compared to evaluate the effectiveness of ICT and AI tools in improving English proficiency and employability skills. The pre- and post-assessments were provided measurable data on changes in the participants' proficiency and skills. Additionally, interviews were offer valuable insights into their personal experiences with the tools, helping to assess the overall impact of the intervention. The results will contribute to understanding the potential benefits of these technologies in rural engineering education.

COTTON'S EMPLOYABILITY SKILLS FRAMEWORK

Cotton's (2001) Employability Skills Framework, developed by Kathleen Cotton, is a comprehensive model that identifies and categorizes the key skills, attitudes, and competencies essential for individuals to secure, retain, and excel in employment. The framework focuses on both foundational skills and workplace-specific abilities, highlighting attributes that are transferable across various industries and job roles.

This model provides educators and employers with a structured approach to preparing individuals for the workforce, ensuring they are equipped with the necessary skills to meet the demands of modern workplaces. Cotton's framework is particularly valuable in fostering a holistic development of employees, emphasizing not just technical expertise, but also critical personal, social, and communication skills.

The Employability Skills Framework is widely recognized and serves as a foundational tool for shaping curricula and training programs. It underscores the importance of competencies such as

problem-solving, teamwork, communication, and adaptability, which are crucial for success in any career. By focusing on these broader competencies, the framework ensures that individuals are prepared for the dynamic and evolving nature of the global job market.

S. No	Skill Category	Specific Skills
1	Personal Management Skills	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Time management - Self-management - Goal setting - Work ethic
2	Communication Skills	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Written communication (e.g., emails, reports, memos) - Oral communication (e.g., presentations, meetings) - Listening skills - Non-verbal communication (e.g., body language, tone)
3	Teamwork Skills	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Collaboration - Working effectively in diverse teams - Conflict resolution and negotiation
4	Problem Solving Skills	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Analytical thinking - Creativity and innovation - Decision making - Initiative and independent thinking
5	Technical Skills	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Digital literacy and use of ICT tools (e.g., word processing, spreadsheets, internet research) - Application of technical knowledge in practical situations
6	Interpersonal Skills	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Emotional intelligence - Adaptability and flexibility - Networking
7	Leadership and Management Skills	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Supervisory skills - Motivation and delegation - Project management
8	Organizational Skills	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Prioritizing and multitasking - Planning and coordinating activities - Attention to detail

Table -2: Cotton's (2001) Employability Skills Framework

Key Components of Cotton's Employability Skills Framework

Cotton's (2001) Employability Skills Framework offers a comprehensive model for the essential skills required for success in the workforce. It covers a broad range of competencies, extending beyond technical knowledge to include personal management, communication, and teamwork skills. The framework is designed to highlight the critical skills that contribute to workplace performance and employability.

1. **Wide Scope:** The framework emphasizes a diverse set of skills, including both basic competencies and advanced interpersonal attributes, vital for thriving in the workplace (Cotton, 2001).
2. **Workplace Relevance:** The skills identified are highly applicable in the real-world work environment, making them directly impactful for enhancing individual performance and employability (Cotton, 2001).
3. **Transferable Skills:** The skills emphasized in the framework are transferable across various job sectors, ensuring their continued relevance in an evolving job market (Cotton, 2001).

This framework is especially valuable for developing training programs aimed at improving the employability of students, such as rural engineering professionals, and serves as a guideline for bridging the gap between academic training and industry requirements.

Cotton's Framework Focus Areas

Cotton (2001) categorizes employability skills into three key areas: basic skills, higher-order thinking skills, and affective skills and traits.

1. Basic Skills

- **Reading, Writing, and Arithmetic:** The ability to understand and apply written and numerical information.
- **Listening and Speaking:** Effective communication in both verbal and written forms.
- **Computer Literacy:** Basic skills in using digital tools and technologies.

2. Higher-Order Thinking Skills

- **Critical Thinking:** The ability to evaluate and analyze information in order to make reasoned decisions.
- **Problem-Solving:** Identifying challenges and applying appropriate strategies for resolution.
- **Decision-Making:** Choosing the best course of action based on available information.
- **Learning to Learn:** Adapting to new information and striving for continuous self-improvement.

3. Affective Skills and Traits

- **Responsibility and Dependability:** Meeting obligations, fulfilling duties, and demonstrating reliability.
- **Teamwork:** Collaborating effectively with others to achieve collective goals.
- **Flexibility and Adaptability:** Responding positively to change and challenges.

- **Self-Esteem and Self-Management:** Showing confidence and taking responsibility for one's actions.
- **Ethics and Integrity:** Upholding high standards of honesty and ethical behavior in the workplace.

Relevance of Cotton's Framework in Education

Cotton's (2001) framework emphasizes the importance of educational institutions in preparing students for the workforce by focusing on:

- **Curriculum Integration:** Incorporating employability skills into academic and vocational programs.
- **Experiential Learning:** Offering real-world learning opportunities through internships, group projects, and practical simulations.
- **Assessment and Feedback:** Regularly evaluating students' progress and providing constructive feedback to aid in their development of employability skills.

Cotton's Framework in the Context of Rural Engineering Students

For rural engineering students, particularly in Telangana's Adilabad, Karimnagar, and Warangal districts, Cotton's (2001) framework provides a practical approach to bridging the gap between academic learning and industry demands. This includes:

- **Basic Skills Development:** Emphasizing English proficiency and technical writing through the use of ICT tools to improve communication skills.
- **Critical Thinking and Problem-Solving:** Engaging students with project-based learning and case studies from industry to develop practical problem-solving skills.
- **Soft Skills Training:** Organizing workshops focused on teamwork, adaptability, and workplace ethics.

Integrating Cotton's (2001) Employability Skills Framework into curricula allows educational institutions to prepare students for the workforce by fostering a holistic approach to skill development that includes technical, cognitive, and interpersonal competencies.

Integrating ICT and AI for Enhancing Speaking and Writing Skills

To enhance speaking and writing skills among rural engineering students, a combination of ICT tools and AI applications can be effectively utilized (Sharma & Kaur, 2020; Kumar, 2019). These technologies offer personalized learning opportunities, encourage collaboration, and support professional development, helping students acquire essential communication skills for global employability.

ICT Tools and Their Applications

Tool	Purpose	Relevance to Skills	Features
Google Workspace (Docs, Slides, Meet)	Facilitates collaborative writing, editing, and online presentations.	Useful for drafting reports, abstracts, and mock interview sessions.	- Real-time collaboration. - Feedback and suggestion tools. - Presentation creation.
Canva	Simplifies the creation of visually appealing resumes, reports, and presentations.	Enhances the professional quality of documents and visuals.	- Customizable templates. - Easy-to-use design interface.
Moodle or Google Classroom	Serves as a platform for sharing learning resources and managing assignments.	Organizes training materials and supports submission of speaking and writing tasks.	- Resource management. - Quizzes and announcements.
Padlet	Provides an interactive digital space for brainstorming and collaboration.	Encourages teamwork on vocabulary-building and idea-sharing activities.	- Multimedia-supported brainstorming. - Interactive discussion boards.
Kahoot!	Makes learning engaging through interactive quizzes and games.	Reinforces grammar, vocabulary, and comprehension.	- Real-time quizzes and feedback. - Gamified learning activities.
Grammarly (Web or App)	Enhances the quality of writing by correcting grammar, tone, and style.	Useful for refining emails, cover letters, and technical reports.	- Instant grammar checks. - Suggestions for tone and clarity.
VoiceThread	Supports asynchronous speaking practice with peer and instructor feedback.	Helps students improve presentations through recorded practice.	- Audio and video recording. - Interactive feedback options.
Loom	Allows recording and reviewing of speeches and presentations.	Enables students to self-assess and refine their delivery.	- Screen and audio recording. - Shareable links for feedback.
Microsoft OneNote	Helps organize drafts and ideas systematically.	Useful for drafting reports and planning presentations.	- Digital notebooks with multimedia integration.
Duolingo or HelloTalk	Provides practice for improving grammar, vocabulary, and pronunciation.	Strengthens language skills through consistent and engaging exercises.	- Gamified language learning. - Community interaction.

Table-3: Indicating Module of AI tools & It's Usage

(Source: <https://www.futurelearn.com>)

Benefits of ICT Tools

- 1. Engaged Learning and Collaboration:**
Tools like Google Workspace, Padlet, and VoiceThread facilitate active collaboration between students and instructors, fostering a more interactive and engaging learning experience.
- 2. Easy Access and Scalable Learning Resources:**
Platforms such as Moodle and Google Classroom provide seamless access to educational materials, ensuring that students in rural areas can easily access and engage with course content.
- 3. Increased Motivation through Gamification:**
Apps like Kahoot! and Duolingo use gamification techniques to encourage students to consistently practice their language skills, making the learning process more enjoyable and motivating.
- 4. Real-Time Feedback and Self-Improvement:**
Tools like Grammarly and Loom deliver instant feedback on writing and speaking, allowing students to make immediate improvements and learn from their mistakes.
- 5. Development of Professional Skills:**
Applications such as Canva and Google Slides allow students to produce high-quality presentations and documents, enhancing their professional communication and technical skills, which are essential for career readiness.

Integrating these ICT tools with AI-powered solutions like Perplexity.AI, Any Summary, and Gemini by Google provides a holistic approach to skill development. These tools focus on improving communication, teamwork, and technical proficiency, in line with Cotton's (2001) Employability Skills Framework for English for Specific Purposes (ESP). Together, they help bridge the gap between academic learning and industry demands, ultimately enhancing students' career prospects.

IMPLICATIONS OF THE STUDY

The results of this study present several important implications:

- **Personalized and Scalable Learning:** The integration of ICT and AI into rural education offers the potential to provide more personalized, accessible, and scalable English language instruction, specifically addressing the diverse needs of rural students.
- **Enhancing Employability Skills:** This research could play a pivotal role in narrowing the employability skills gap, thus contributing to the creation of a highly skilled, globally competitive workforce among rural engineering professionals.
- **ESP Framework in ELT:** The findings suggest that the ESP framework can serve as an effective model for developing future English Language Teaching (ELT) curricula, designed to meet the professional requirements of specific fields, particularly in rural settings.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the study's findings, the following recommendations are put forward:

- **Enhancement of ICT and AI Infrastructure:** It is crucial to invest in ICT and AI infrastructure across rural educational institutions to ensure that these tools are accessible and effectively integrated into teaching and learning processes.
- **Creation of Localized ESP Materials:** Tailored ESP-based educational materials should be developed, addressing the specific needs of rural engineering professionals, to bridge the gap between academic knowledge and industry expectations.
- **Professional Development for Educators:** Educators should undergo specialized training to effectively utilize ICT and AI tools in their teaching. This would maximize the educational impact of these technologies and better equip students for the modern workforce.

SCOPE FOR FURTHER RESEARCH

Future research could extend the insights from this study by exploring the following areas:

- **Long-Term Outcomes:** Investigating the long-term effects of ICT and AI tools on the professional growth of rural engineering graduates, particularly in terms of their ability to apply the skills gained through these tools in the workplace.
- **Applicability to Broader Contexts:** Further studies could explore how the model used in this research can be applied to other rural areas in India or internationally, evaluating its transferability to different educational contexts and professional fields.
- **Comparative Studies:** Conducting comparative studies between regions with varying levels of ICT and AI integration could provide deeper insights into how these technologies influence educational outcomes and employability in rural settings.
- **Impact of Socio-Cultural Factors:** Future research could examine how socio-cultural factors affect the effectiveness of ICT and AI tools in rural education, providing further guidance for tailoring these tools to the unique challenges of specific regions.

CONCLUSIONS

The integration of ICT and AI tools into English language teaching holds significant promise for enhancing both English proficiency and employability skills among rural engineering professionals. This study supports the applicability of the ESP framework in addressing the specific language and professional needs of rural engineers, particularly in improving communication and technical writing skills.

The findings demonstrate that ICT and AI tools offer a dynamic, engaging, and accessible approach to bridging skill gaps, especially in rural areas where traditional educational resources may be scarce. These technologies allow students to receive immediate feedback, develop critical soft skills, and engage in practical learning experiences, which better prepare them for the global workforce.

Given the ongoing challenges in rural education and skill development, this research highlights the transformative role of technology in creating more inclusive and effective learning environments. By continuing to invest in ICT infrastructure, educator training, and the development of localized learning materials, these tools can significantly enhance the educational experiences of rural students, thereby improving their professional prospects and career outcomes.

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